

DIELECTRIC CONSTANT AND DIPOLE MOMENT: CHROMONES, FLAVONES AND BENZYLIDENE-COUMARANONES

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The dielectric constants and densities of 2:6-dimethyl- γ -pyrone, 2-methyl-5-hydroxychromone and 2-methyl-7-methoxychromone, four flavones and two benzylidene-coumaranones have been measured at various concentrations and various temperatures. The dipole moments have been deduced by applying the new equation, and the values obtained have been compared with the values calculated theoretically.

The moment of 2:6-dimethyl- γ -pyrone in benzene solution was measured by Hunter and Partington (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 87) and by Govinda Rao (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1936, 4A, 687). In the present work the data of these authors have been recalculated by applying the new equation. The dielectric constants and densities of 2-methyl-5-hydroxychromone and 2-methyl-7-methoxychromone, 4'-methoxyflavone, 4'-methoxy-6-methylflavone, 4'-benzyloxyflavone, 6-benzoyl-4'-methoxyflavone, 4'-methoxy- and 4'-methoxy-5-methylbenzylidene-coumaranones in benzene have been measured over a range of temperatures at various concentrations.

The moments of these compounds have been measured for the first time. The results are shown in the tables.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Thiophene-free benzene was made as described previously (*this Journal*, 1960, 37, 1). It was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride and frozen. The portion that froze at 5.5° was finally distilled over P₂O₅.

2-Methyl-5-hydroxychromone was recrystallised from alcohol till the observed m.p. agreed with the literature value. In the case of the rest of the compounds, the samples available were combustion samples and were used as such.

TABLE I

	Obs. M.P.	Lit. M.P.
2-Methyl-5-hydroxychromone	92°	92°
2-Methyl-7-methoxychromone	113°	113°
4'-Methoxyflavone	157°	157-58°
6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavone	170°	170°
4'-Benzyloxyflavone	190°	190°
6-Benzoyl-4'-methoxyflavone	205°	205°
4'-Methoxybenzylidene-coumaranone	134°	133-53-4-5
4'-Methoxy-5-methylbenzylidene-coumaranone	152°	152°

TABLE IV

*7-Methoxy-2-methylchromone.

Solvent: benzene. $P_2 = 207.04$.

Temp.	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}
		$w_2 = 0.007597$				$w_2 = 0.009872$		
25°	2.358	0.8756	2604	3.61	2.381	0.8746	2601	3.61
30°	2.346	0.8696	2554	3.67	2.367	0.8686	2543	3.59
35°	2.333	0.8638	2528	3.61	2.356	0.8626	2524	3.61
40°	2.322	0.8576	2503	3.62	2.342	0.8564	2504	3.62
45°	2.309	0.8518	2478	3.63	2.329	0.8504	2466	3.62

* Present work.

TABLE V

*4'-Methoxyflavone.

Solvent: benzene. $P_2 = 289.5$.

Temp.	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}
		$w_2 = 0.01047$				$w_2 = 0.009292$		
25°	2.330	0.8762	1807	2.87	2.322	0.8754	1765	2.83
30°	2.317	0.8700	1759	2.85	2.309	0.8692	1738	2.83
35°	2.304	0.8638	1711	2.83	2.298	0.8630	1710	2.83
40°	2.292	0.8576	1711	2.85	2.285	0.8563	1693	2.82
45°	2.280	0.8514	1663	2.82	2.272	0.8506	1656	2.82

*Present work.

TABLE VI

*6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavone.

Solvent: benzene. $P_2 = 303.5$.

Temp.	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}
		$w_2 = 0.0044303$				$w_2 = 0.0072417$		
20°	2.336	0.87882	1744	2.78	2.351	0.88029	1765	2.80
25°	2.327	0.87134	1744	2.80	2.342	0.87466	1729	2.79
30°	2.317	0.86721	1684	2.76	2.332	0.86383	1692	2.77
35°	2.308	0.86102	1684	2.79	2.322	0.86263	1655	2.76
40°	2.298	0.85483	1624	2.75	2.311	0.85613	1618	2.74
45°	2.288	0.84864	1624	2.77	2.301	0.85023	1581	2.72
50°	2.278	0.84245	1563	2.73	2.290	0.84403	1545	2.71

* Present work.

TABLE VII

*4'-Benzoyloxyflavone.

Solvent: benzene. $w_2 = 0.006395$. $P_2 = 381.4$.

Temp.	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}
25°	2.335	0.8772	3697	4.25
30°	2.321	0.8708	3646	4.25
35°	2.310	0.8646	3594	4.25
40°	2.297	0.8584	3491	4.21
45°	2.283	0.8520	3441	4.21

* Present work.

TABLE VIII

*6-Benzoyl-4'-methoxyflavone.

Solvent: benzene. $w_2 = 0.006726$. $P_2 = 406.8$.

Temp.	ϵ_{12}	d_{12}	P_2	μ_{new}
25°	2.315	0.8760	2755	3.57
30°	2.302	0.8702	2702	3.56
35°	2.291	0.8644	2650	3.55
40°	2.280	0.8586	2606	3.54
45°	2.269	0.8527	2543	3.52

TABLE IX

*4'-Methoxybenzylidene-coumaranone.

Solvent: benzene. $P_1 = 284.9$.

Temp.	ϵ_{12} .	d_{12} .	P_2 .	μ_{new} .	ϵ_{12} .	d_{12} .	P_2 .	μ_{new} .	ϵ_{12} .	d_{12} .	P_2 .	μ_{new} .
	$w_2 = 0.01495$.				$w_2 = 0.01910$				$w_2 = 0.02609$.			
25°	2.348	0.8784	1670	2.75	2.371	0.8754	1690	2.76	2.407	0.8814	1692	2.77
30°	2.336	0.8730	1637	2.73	2.359	0.8738	1678	2.72	2.393	0.8753	1673	2.77
35°	2.325	0.8674	1620	2.74	2.346	0.8682	1625	2.75	2.378	0.8702	1625	2.75
40°	2.314	0.8622	1586	2.73	2.333	0.8630	1590	2.74	2.365	0.8648	1586	2.73
45°	2.303	0.8568	1570	2.73	2.321	0.8576	1559	2.71	2.353	0.8594	1576	2.74

* Present work.

TABLE X

*4'-Methoxy-5-methylbenzylidene-coumaranone.

Solvent: benzene. $P_1 = 303.5$.

Temp.	ϵ_{12} .	d_{12} .	P_2 .	μ_{new} .	ϵ_{12} .	d_{12} .	P_2 .	μ_{new} .
	$w_2 = 0.007415$.				$w_2 = 0.008405$.			
25°	2.311	0.8760	1724	2.78	2.316	0.8766	1711	2.77
30°	2.298	0.8702	1689	2.77	2.304	0.8708	1679	2.76
35°	2.287	0.8642	1652	2.73	2.292	0.8648	1647	2.75
40°	2.276	0.8582	1616	2.74	2.281	0.8588	1615	2.74
45°	2.263	0.8522	1581	2.72	2.268	0.8528	1584	2.73

* Present work.

TABLE XI

Moments.

Compound.	Solvent.	μ_{new}		μ_{calc} .	μ .
		1kT.	1.5kT.		
2:6-Dimethyl- γ -pyrone	Benzene*	3.78		2.16 I	4.49
	Benzene†	3.53			4.05
2-Methyl-5-hydroxychromone	Benzene**	3.32		3.25 I	
		3.60		5.12 II	
		(4.2)		4.18	
2-Methyl-7-methoxychromone	Benzene**	3.61		3.85	
4'-Methoxyflavone	Benzene**	2.83	3.47	3.30	
6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavone	Benzene**	2.84	3.48	3.30	
4'-Benzoyloxyflavone	Benzene**			3.30 II	
6-Benzoyl-4'-methoxyflavone	Benzene**	4.24		6.2 III	
4'-Methoxybenzylidene-coumaranone	Benzene**	3.58		3.92	
4'-Methoxy-5-methylbenzylidene-coumaranone	Benzene**	2.75		2.90	
		2.75		2.90	

* Govinda Rao, *loc. cit.*† Hunter and Partington, *loc. cit.*

** Present work.

C—O (1) is reduced to a value of 0.74 because of induction from C—O (2), the effect of induction from C—O (3) being negligible. C—O (2) is reduced to a moment of 0.555 because of induction from C—O (1) and C—O (3). C—O (3) is reduced to a value of 1.295 because of induction from C—O (2), the effect of induction from C—O (1) being very small. C=O and O—H remain unaffected, and have the moment values of 2.90 and 2.40 respectively.

Structure (I): The moment along C_5-C_6 is 3.14 (0.74 + 2.40) and that along C—O (3) is 4.195 (1.295 + 2.90). The resultant of these two is 3.78. This resultant together with the moment 0.555 along C_5-C_6 will give the molecular moment, the value of which is 3.25.

Structure (II): The moment along C_5-C_6 is 0.555 and that along C—O (3) is 4.195. The resultant of these two is 3.947. This resultant together with the moment of 1.66 along C_5-C_6 (2.4-0.74) gives the molecular moment, the value of which is 5.12.

The observed moment of the compound varies with temperature, the value being 3.32 to 3.60. It seems that with increase of temperature, the hydrogen bond breaks up and the contribution due to structure (II) becomes more and more. The moment increases with temperature and asymptotically reaches a value of 4.2 at a higher temperature. This value compares with the mean of the two values for structure (I) and structure (II).

2-Methyl-7-methoxychromone

The moment of 2-methyl-7-methoxychromone in benzene has been measured for the first time. The new moment is 3.61, which is independent of temperature and concentration. The moment can be theoretically calculated for this compound. The two possible structures for this compound are shown below.

C—O (1) and C—O (2) are each reduced to 0.74 because of induction. C—O (3) and C—O (4) are each reduced to 0.99 because of induction. The effect of induction of C—O (1) and C—O (2) on C—O (3) and C—O (4) and *vice versa* is very very small. The moment of C=O is 2.90.

Structure (I): The resultant 0.74 of C—O (1) and C—O (2) adds on to the resultant 1.14 of C—O (3) and C—O (4) and gives a moment of 1.88. This together with the moment 2.9 of C=O gives the molecular moment, the value of which is 1.02.

Structure (II): The resultant of C—O (1) and C—O (2) acts in a direction opposite to the resultant of C—O (3) and C—O (4) and gives a resultant moment of 0.40 in the direction of C=O. The net molecular moment is 3.30.

In addition to these two structures, there may be a third dipolar structure as in the case of 2:6-dimethyl- γ -pyrone.

(III)

Structure (III) : The full moment of C=O is 5.8. The resultant of C—O (1) and C—O (2) combines with the resultant of C—O (3) and C—O (4), and gives a moment value of 1.88. This together with the full moment of C=O bond affords the molecular moment, the value of which is 3.92.

It appears that only structures (II) and (III) contribute to the molecular moment. The mean of the values for these two structures is 3.61, which compares with the observed value of 3.61. It appears that in this compound, as in the case of 2:6-dimethyl- γ -pyrone, the ionic character of C=O bond has increased to 75% instead of the normal value of 50%. The results are summarised in Table XI.

4'-Methoxyflavone

The moment of 4'-methoxyflavone in benzene solution is 2.83, as obtained by the new equation. The moment has been measured for the first time and is independent of temperature and concentration. The compound can have two possible structures, structure (I) and structure (II).

(I)

(II)

C—O (1) and C—O (2) are each reduced to a moment of 0.74 because of mutual induction. Similarly C—O (3) and C—O (4) are each reduced to a value of 0.99 due to mutual induction. The effect of induction of C—O (1) and C—O (2) on C—O (3) and C—O (4) and *vice versa* is negligible.

Structure (I) : The resultant of C—O (1) and C—O (2) is 0.74. The resultant of C—O (3) and C—O (4) is 1.14. These two, being parallel, add on and give a moment value of 1.88. This, together with the moment of 2.90 of C=O, gives 1.02 as the value of the molecular moment.

Structure (II) : The resultant of 0.74 of C—O (1) and C—O (2) is parallel to and in opposite direction of the resultant 1.14 of C—O (3) and C—O (4). The net resultant is 0.40 in the direction of C=O. The molecular moment is thus 3.30.

The observed moment of 2.83 may be increased to a value of 3.47 by increasing $2j+1=2$ ($1kT$) to $2j+1=3$ ($1.5kT$). This value compares with the value calculated for structure (II).

6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavone

The new moment of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavone in benzene is 2.76, which is independent of temperature and concentration. The moment has been measured for the first time.

6-Methyl 4'-methoxyflavone has two structures similar to those of 4'-methoxyflavone. The moment for structure (I) is 1.02 and that for structure (II) is 3.30. The observed moment of 2.84 can be increased to a value of 3.48 by increasing $2j+1=2$ ($1kT$) to $2j+1=3$ ($1.5kT$). This compares with the value calculated for structure (II).

6-Benzoyl-4'-methoxyflavone

The moment of 6-benzoyl-4'-methoxyflavone, as obtained by the new equation, is 3.55, which is independent of temperature. The moment of this compound has been determined for the first time.

C—O (1) and C—O (2) are each reduced to a moment of 0.74, and C—O (3) and C—O (4) are each reduced to a moment of 0.99 because of mutual induction. The effect of induction due to C—O (1) and C—O (2) on C—O (3) and C—O (4) and *vice versa* is negligible. The bonds C=O (1) and C=O (2) are also unaffected, as the induction is very small.

Structure (I): The resultant 0.74 of C—O (1) and C—O (2) and 1.14 of C—O (3) and C—O (4) add on to give a moment of 1.88. The resultant of C=O (1) and C=O (2) is 5.80. The resultant of the two is the molecular moment. the value of which is 3.92.

Structure (II): The resultant of C—O (1) and C—O (2) and of C—O (3) and C—O (4) oppose each other and give a moment value of 0.4. This together with the resultant 5.8 of C=O (1) and C=O (2) affords a value of 6.20, which is the value of the molecular moment.

Structure (III): The moment of C=O (1) cancels that of C=O (2). The resultant 0.74 of C—O (1) and C—O (2) adds on with the resultant 1.14 of C—O (3) and C—O (4) and provides the value of 1.88, which is the molecular moment.

Structure (IV): C=O (1) cancels C=O (2). The resultant of C—O (1) and C—O (2) opposes the resultant of C—O (3) and C—O (4) and gives 0.4 as the value of the molecular moment.

The observed moment of 3.55 indicates that structure (I) predominates with little contribution from structures (II) and (IV).

4'-Benzyloxyflavone

The new moment of 4'-benzyloxyflavone in benzene is 4.23, which is independent of temperature. The moment has been determined for the first time.

C—O (1) and C—O (2) are each reduced to a moment of 0.74 because of induction. Similarly, C—O (3) and C—O (4) are each reduced to a value of 0.99 due to induction. The effect of induction of C—O (3) and C—O (4) on C—O (1) and C—O (2) and *vice versa* is very small, and so is neglected. C=O remains unaffected.

Structure (I) : The resultant of C—O (1) and C—O (2) is 0.74. The resultant of C—O (3) and C—O (4) is 1.14. The two are parallel and in the same direction and so give a net moment of 1.88. This together with the moment of 2.90 of C=O affords a moment value of 1.02, which is the molecular moment.

Structure (II) : The resultant 0.74 of C—O (1) and C—O (2) opposes the resultant 1.14 of C—O (3) and C—O (4) and provides a resultant of 0.40 in the direction of C=O. The molecular moment is obtained by the addition of 0.40 with the moment of 2.90 of the C=O bond. The molecular moment is 3.30.

In addition to the above two structures, 4'-benzyloxyflavone may have a structure of the type (III) similar to one suggested by Berson (*loc. cit.*) for dimethyl- γ -pyrone.

The resultant of C—O (1) and C—O (2) opposes the resultant of C—O (3) and C—O (4) and gives a net moment of 0.40 in the direction of C—O⁻. The resultant moment is 6.20 (5.8 + 0.4).

The observed moment of 4.23 indicates that structures (II) and (III) predominate with no contribution from structure (I). It appears that structure (III) contributes to the molecular moment to a large extent, nearly 50%, indicating that the ionic character of C=O bond in this compound is increased to about 75%. The results are summarised in Table XI.

4'-Methoxybenzylidene-coumaranone

The new moment of 4'-methoxybenzylidene-coumaranone in benzene is 2.76, which is independent of temperature and concentration. The moment of this compound has been determined for the first time.

C—O (1) and C—O (2) are each reduced to a moment value of 0.99 and C—O (3) and C—O (4) to a value of 0.99 because of mutual induction. The induction of C—O (1) and C—O (2) on C—O (3) and C—O (4) and *vice versa* is negligible.

Structure (I) : The moment of C—O (1) and C—O (2) is 1.14 and that of C—O (3) and C—O (4) is 1.14. The two are parallel and in the same direction and so add up to give a moment of 2.28. This together with the moment 2.9 of C=O gives the molecular moment, the value of which is 0.62.

Structure (II) : The resultant 1.14 of C—O (1) and C—O (2) and 1.14 of C—O (3) and C—O (4) are parallel but in opposite direction. The resultant of the two is zero. This together with the moment 2.9 of C=O gives 2.9 as the value for the molecular moment.

The observed moment of 2.75 indicates that the molecular moment is entirely due to structure (II) with a small contribution from structure (I).

4'-Methoxy-5-methylbenzylidene-coumaranone

The moment of 4'-methoxy-5-methylbenzylidene-coumaranone in benzene has been measured for the first time. The moment obtained by the new equation is 2.75, which is independent of temperature and concentration. The compound has two structures, similar to those of 4'-methoxybenzylidene-coumaranone.

The moment calculated for structure (I) is 0.62 and that for structure (II) is 2.90. The observed value of 2.75 shows that structure (II) predominates with very little contribution from structure (I).